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Local and express probing of enzymatic activity using functional plasmon active optical fiber

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ABSTRACT

Enzymes are very essential part of living organisms and are also actively used by humanity in various technological processes. The activity of enzymes, especially those isolated from microorganisms, can vary significantly from one to another source. Therefore, it is necessary to develop methods for express and the least invasive detection of enzymatic activity. In this work, we propose a biochemical sensor of enzymatic activity created on the basis of a plasmon-active optical fiber probe covalently functionalized with an enzyme-sensitive organic molecules, immersed in the solution, containing (or not) β -glucosidase at various experimental conditions. In the presence of enzyme, the grafted to plasmon-active surface organic moieties undergo cleavage of C-O bond leading to a change in the local environment of the optical fiber probe and to a shift in the spectral position plasmon absorption band, monitored in the back-reflected light. The functionality of the created optical fiber probe was tested at various experimental conditions, including the variation of the external temperature or pH, and results obtained correspond well with results of traditional biochemical tests. It is possible to determine the presence of the enzyme, estimate its concentration, and suppress its activity under unfavourable experimental conditions. The proposed approach allows in site enzyme detection and cheap and express analysis, with minimal disruption of enzymatic systems.

1. Introduction

Enzymes as a natural, biological catalysts can significantly accelerate the chemical reactions [1]. In addition to their extremely important biological function in living organisms, the enzymes find enormous application in biochemical reactors, where they are used for catalysis of a wide range of commercially important processes including the preparation of food products and additives, modification of antibiotics, preparation of various sensors and analytical devices as well as for production of various cleaning products [2–6]. For such goals the various simple sources of enzymes are commonly used, but the most of “commercial” enzymes are extracted from bacteria or plants because of technical, economic, and ethical reasons [7,8]. However, even in the case of extra- or intra-cellular bacterial-delivered enzymes, their activity

can be varied significantly, even under apparently similar conditions of bacterial strain growth or enzymes isolation and purification [9–12]. The variation of activity can be observed for different microbes or microorganism but even between the different strains as a function of microorganism development and surrounding conditions. The uncertainty in enzymes activity is especially pronounced in the case of bacterial enzymes [13,14]. The enzymes activity can also gradually decrease during the enzymes use due to their gradual degradation [15, 16]. For all these reasons the enzymes activity should be carefully monitored, immediately after enzymes production or during their utilization.

The measurements of enzyme activity are commonly performed by estimation of the substrate(s) consumption but such methods requires the utilization of calorimetric or various spectroscopic techniques [17,

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18]. Alternatively, enzymatic activity can be estimated using ELISA-based methods [19,20]. In all cases, such approaches require the sampling of an analytical probe, as well as their purification. In this way it is almost impossible to estimate the enzyme activity directly in situ, e. g. directly in the reactor or in the tissue or microorganisms suspension.

In this work we propose a specially modified plasmon-active optical fiber-based sensor [21–24] for the local, simple, and express estimation of enzyme activity. Our solution is based on the probe molecules directly grafted to a plasmon-active surface. Under the enzyme action the probe molecules undergo the chemical change's, leading to the local changes in refractive index of close environment, which changes are observed via a shift of plasmon absorption band [25–28]. As a model reaction we choose the estimation of β -Glucosidase activity, but the similar approach can be also used for the estimation of alternative enzymes activity. The main aim of our work is to show that enzyme(s) activity can be determined in a simple, express, and „local“ way, with the utilisation of proposed approach.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Multimode plastic-clad silica optical (PCS) fibers were purchased from CeramOptec (Germany) with core and buffer/cladding diameters of 200 and 230/500 μm . Sodium acetate buffer solution (pH 5.2 ± 0.1 ; 3 M), water (EMD Millipore), glycerol (99.5 %, Penta), ethanol (> 96 %), methanol (99.8 %), β -Glucosidase from almonds (lyophilized, powder, ≥ 4 U/mg), β -Glucosidase Activity Assay Kit 3-Iodobenzotri-fluoride, toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate, *m*-CPBA, tetrafluoroethylene, BSA (≥ 96 %), dichloromethane were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. Au target (99,99 %) was purchased from the SAFINA, a.s. Czech Republic.

2.2. Sample preparation

On area of optical fiber, the cladding was thermally removed (2 cm length) and naked cores were purified by washing with deionized water, acetone, and methanol. The naked fiber core was homogeneously coated by Au thin films (ca 20 nm thickness) using plasma sputtering using home-made rotating device installed inside the Quorum Q300 T (England) chamber. The length of plasmon active area and gold thickness were preliminary optimised to reach the optimal value of the intensity and half-width of the plasmon absorption band (Figs. S1 and S2). The film of Ag (thickness approx. 100 nm) was sputtered on the polished end of the fiber and fixed with a thick PMMA layer to form a mirror there. For the introduction of enzyme sensitivity the surface grafting using novel reagent (3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)(4-(β -D-glucopyranosyloxy)phenyl)iodonium tosylate (GlyIS) [29] was performed (synthetic procedure and characterisation of GlyIS is described in SI).

2.3. Surface modification of optical fiber sensors using iodonium salt

The plasmon-active optical fiber was connected to a laser source with a wavelength corresponding to the maximum of plasmon absorption band (730 nm) and placed in a solution of GlyIS (6 mM) in a methanol/water (2:1) solution under continuous illumination. When laser radiation passed through the optical fiber, a surface plasmon was excited on the Au surface. Plasmon triggering of GlyIS molecules led to homolysis of the C-I bond with the formation of a highly-reactive radicals, which were immediately grafted to the Au surface.

2.4. Samples characterization techniques

Vis-NIR absorbance spectra of the samples were measured using a HR2000 (Ocean Optics) spectrometer in the 400–1000 nm wavelength range and AvaLight-DHS light source (Avantes). Spectrometer and light

source were connected to the fiber probe using Y-junction and Standard SMA905 Connector (Thorlabs). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) (LYRA3 GMU, Tescan, CR) were collected at the operating voltage of 10 kV and a beam current of 600 pA. Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectra were measured on Nicolet iS5 Spectrometer. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific XPS NEXSA spectrometer equipped with an Al K Alpha X-ray monochromatic emitter with an energy of 1486.6 eV. Survey spectra were recorded using pass energy of 200 eV with energy resolution of 1 eV. High-resolution spectra (C1s, F1s, O1s, Au4f) were collected using pass energy of 50 eV and a resolution of 0.1 eV. The spectra were calibrated against the C1s peak set at 284.8 eV.

The surface morphology and thin layers thickness were measured by peak force AFM technique using Icon (Bruker) microscope.

2.5. Detection of enzymatic activity using the present approach

First, the enzyme (β -Glucosidase from almonds, powder, ≥ 4 U/mg) was dissolved in sodium acetate buffer. Commonly, 0.2–0.002 U/L of enzyme in 5 mL of sodium acetate was used, except otherwise mentioned concentrations. The optical probe was immersed in the enzyme solution and changes of Vis-NIR absorption spectra were measured continuously. Experiments were performed at different temperatures (20–80 °C range) for the estimation of temperature dependency of enzyme activity. For the estimation of pH dependencies, the sodium acetate buffer was replaced by diluted solutions of KOH or H_2SO_4 . All experiments (temperature and pH dependencies) were repeated in triplicate.

2.6. Estimation of enzymatic activity at different pH and temperatures using commercial kit

For control evaluation of the activity of β -glucosidase (at various temperatures and pH) the β -Glucosidase activity assay kit was used. To 400 μL of the Buffer and 16 μL of β -NPG substrate were added 40 μL of each β -glucosidase (50 U/L), which was then incubated at different temperatures for 20 min with shaking. The reaction was stopped by adding 500 μL of 2 M Na_2CO_3 . The activity of β -glucosidase was evaluated spectrophotometrically by measuring the peak intensity at 420 nm. For evaluation of pH on β -glucosidase activity the experiments were performed with the same amount of reagents, but instead of buffer, solutions with different pH (diluted KOH and H_2SO_4 solutions) were used. The samples were incubated at 37 °C. Before absorbance measurement, the pH was adjusted to 7 using the addition of phosphate buffer solution (linear correction on concentration changes due to reaction volume changes was subsequently used).

2.7. Estimation of fiber sensor stability

Antibiofouling properties were evaluated by immersing the modified and pristine fibers in a BSA solution (10^{-3} M in PBS buffer) for 180 min. at room temperature. After immersion, the fibers were thoroughly rinsed with deionised water, dried, and subsequently tested. To assess long-term stability, the fibers were stored for a month at 5 °C and the sensor response to the presence of the enzyme was measured every week under standard conditions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Main experimental concept

The schema of main experimental concept used for the estimation of enzyme activity (in particular, β -Glucosidase) is presented in Fig. 1. First, the functional plasmon-active fiber probe was prepared. The naked fiber surface was covered by thin Au layer, leading to the appearance of visible plasmon-absorption band (Fig. 1A). Among the common

Fig. 1. Schema of the preparation of optical fiber based sensor for in-situ estimation of enzyme activity and its operation: plasmon-induced grafting of glycoside chemical moieties (A, B) and their subsequent enzyme-induced cleavage (C, D), both leading to the shift of the wavelength position of plasmon absorption band, which can be read in the light-reflection mode.

plasmon-active metals, (Ag, Cu, and Au), gold was chosen because it was the most chemically stable and having a plasmon resonance peak in a convenient spectral region (from the point of view of commercially available broadband radiation sources and detectors). An adhesive film between the gold and the optical fiber was not introduced so as to avoid the screening of the energy transfer between the photonic and plasmonic modes. In the fiber sensor design, the parameters of the deposited Au layers were additionally optimised (length of plasmon active are – 2 cm and Au thickness – 20 nm) to reach a compromise between the strength of the plasmon absorption band and its half-width (Figs. S1 and S2). For the introduction of enzyme-sensitivity we performed the surface functionalisation, with diaryliodonium salt (referred as GlyIS, see SI). For plasmon surface functionalization and enzyme sensitivity the fibers were connected to laser light source and immersed in the solution of GlyIS. Under the plasmon triggering the cleavage of C-I bond with the formation of highly reactive radicals containing glycoside chemical moiety, occur (Fig. 1B) [30]. The generated radicals are immediately grafted to plasmon-active surface, resulting in its functionalization with a „substrate“ molecule. The prepared structure subsequently served for estimation of enzyme activity (Fig. 1C). In the final step the Ag mirror was deposited on fiber end to enable the local measurement of enzyme activity in the reflected light. Created fibers are subsequently referred as Au-Gly probe. For better clarity, experimental set-up for enzymatic activity estimation with Au-Gly probe utilization is given in Fig. S3.

In the next step, the optical probes were connected to a wide spectrum light source and detector, using the Y-junction and the active part of the Au-Gly probe was immersed in the solution of β -Glucosidase. The enzyme action led to the cleavage of C-O bond and the release of glucose from the plasmon fiber, as is schematically shown in Fig. 1D. As a result,

the local change in the environmental refractive index is induced. Since the position of the plasmon absorption band is a strong function of the surrounding refractive index the local changes of the refractive index (occurred due to the C-O bond cleavage and release of the glucose chemical moiety away from the fiber surface) are accompanied by the shift of plasmon absorption band position. Such a shift can be observed in the reflected light as a shift of the plasmon absorption band (see Fig. 1D, left part) and is expected to be a function of enzyme activity or external conditions (i.e. the kinetic of C-O bond cleavage). In other words, in the proposed sensor design, the enzyme induced cleavage of C-O bond and release of Gly moiety are monitored by plasmonic evanescent wave, excited on the Au covered optical fiber surface.

3.2. Characterization of function plasmon-active optical fiber probe surface

The preparation steps of functional optical fiber surface were confirmed using Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) techniques. First the Vis-NIR measurements confirm that the initial position of plasmon absorption band is red-shifted by ca 30 nm after the Au fibers grafting with Gly chemical moieties (Fig. 2A, Fig. 1B, C). The shift indicated the local change of fiber chemical environment, which can be attributed to the immobilization of functional layer, responsible for the interaction with enzyme. The structure of the grafted chemical moieties was subsequently revealed using FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 2B), which shows the appearance of several characteristic bands. The spectral positions of the

Fig. 2. Verification of the grafting of $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-O-Gly}$ moieties to plasmon active part of optical fiber probe: A – position shift of the plasmon absorption band; B – FTIR spectra measured before and after the surface functionalization (FTIR spectrum of GlyIS is presented for comparison); C – XPS spectra measured before and after the grafting and after the enzyme action; D – SEM and EDX characterization of Au surface morphology and composition before and after the grafting of Gly chemical moieties; E – AFM measured surface morphology (from left to right: Au surface, Au-Gly surface, Au-Gly surface after interaction with enzyme).

bands correspond well with the vibration modes of phenylene ring and glycoside fragment (Table S1). In turn, XPS measurements (Fig. 2C) indicated apparent a significant changes in the surface composition, confirming in this way the grafting of glycoside. We also did not observe the presence of fluor or $-\text{CF}_3$ vibration bands (see Fig. S4), which absence corresponds well with proposed mechanism of unsymmetric IS ((3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)(4-(β -D-glucopyranosyloxy)phenyl)iodonium tosylate) cleavage, presented in Fig. S5 (accompanied by the discussion of the reaction mechanism), and surface functionalization solely with glycoside-containing chemical group. SEM and AFM measurements (Fig. 2D, 2E and Fig. S6) show significant changes of fiber surface

morphology after functional coating immobilization, which otherwise can be expected, since organic layer consisting of relatively large organic molecules was grafted to the fiber surface (Fig. 2). The thickness of organic layer of about 20 nm was determined by scratch test (Fig. S7). Finally, EDX maps of carbon and oxygen distribution (Fig. 2D) reveal the homogeneous coating of Au surface by the functional layer.

3.3. Utilization of Au-Gly fiber probe for the estimation of enzyme activity

In the next step, we proceed to the confirmation of the created fiber probe functionality. As was mentioned above, we chose the enzyme-

triggered cleavage of O-glycoside bond. Such cleavage will result in the glucose release accompanied by the local changes of fiber probe chemical environment. As a result, the red shift of plasmon absorption band emerges, the size of which is to be proportional to the intensity of the O-glycoside bond cleavage, i.e. to the enzyme activity. The shift of plasmon absorption band was monitored in back-reflected light after the fibers immersion in the appropriate medium, making the overall detection procedure extremely simple and express.

First, we estimated the shift of plasmon absorption band immediately after the immersion of fiber to the enzyme solution. The reaction volume of the enzyme solution was 5 mL. Optical measurements were performed *in situ*, and the main results are presented in Fig. 3A, B. As is evident, immediately after the fiber immersion, the shift of plasmon absorption band starts. The spectral features (i.e. position of plasmon absorption band) are related to the characteristic of non-grafted fibers. After certain time the spectral position is stabilized but it still differs slightly from that in the case of unmodified fiber, since the chemical group $-C_6H_4-OH$ remains attached to the plasmon-active surface, Fig. S8. At the initial stage the shift of plasmon absorption band increases linearly with time and shows asymptotic behaviour at later stages (Fig. 3B). As in the classical case of enzymatic activity determination, such behaviour indicates apparent substrate depletion, i.e., all previously grafted chemical moieties are cleaved, and glucose diffuses away from optical fiber surface. The observed shift of plasmon-active fiber is surely a function of β -glucosidase concentration. Almost immediate reaching of saturation plateau was observed for higher enzyme concentration, while for lower concentration the saturation takes approximately 20 min (Fig. 3B). The use of intermediate enzyme

concentrations also resulted in a shift of the plasmon absorption band with a rate characteristic of each specific enzyme concentration. Thus, we can conclude that the concentration or activity of the enzyme can be determined from the kinetics of the optical sensor response. Finally, it should be noted that the observed optical response occurs solely in the presence of enzyme (Fig. S9), clearly confirming the mechanism and specificity of the probe response (presented in Fig. 1C, D).

After confirming the fibers sensitivity to enzyme presence we proceeded to the semi-quantitative estimation of enzyme activity. For this goal we performed a range of experiments, where the enzymes were kept under various conditions, (temperature or pH, including non-optimal ones). Extreme conditions may result in partial or complete enzymes denaturation and loss of their activity. First, the impact of increasing temperature was examined by measurement of the plasmon band shift as a function of the temperature from 20 to 50°C (see Fig. 3C). Each measurement was performed after the 7 min of exposure to particular temperature. The temperature decrease from 24 to 20 °C leads to less pronounced band shift of the indicating the suppression of enzymes activity of β -Glucosidase compared to RT case. The temperature increase up to 50 °C leads to more pronounced band shifts, reflecting an increase of enzyme activity with temperature. It should be noted that in the absence of functional layer (see Fig. S10) the shift of plasmon absorption band also occurs due to the changes of water refractive index, but it is significantly less pronounced than in the above-described case. Further temperature increase leads to enzymes denaturation accompanied with corresponding loss of enzymatic activity. So, prepared fiber sensor probe allows to estimate the activity of enzymes as a function of temperature. Preliminary heating of enzymes (at 90 °C, 3 h) and their subsequent

Fig. 3. A – Vis-NIR optical spectra and gradual shift of plasmon absorption band measured after the probe immersion in the enzyme solution (RT, pH=5.0; enzyme concentration 0.002 U/L); B – position of plasmon absorption band as a function of optical probe interaction time with enzyme solution (RT, pH=5.0); C, D – dependence of the shift of plasmon absorption band and the enzymatic activity on temperature and pH (both measured after 20 min of interaction).

examination with optical fiber probe at RT does not show any changes in the position of plasmon absorption band (see Fig. S11). At this temperature complete and irreversible denaturation of enzyme makes the cleavage of glycoside impossible, as was detected by the proposed fiber probe. The measured temperature dependence of enzymatic activity was also compared with that obtained by common estimation methods based on commercially supplied kit (Fig. S12). Results of these control measurements also indicate the increase of enzyme activity with temperature increase up to 50–60 °C and its subsequent decrease at higher temperatures. So, the present results obtained with our fiber probe correlates well with those of control measurements performed with commercial kit.

Next, we determined the influence of pH on the enzyme activity in the similar way, i.e. with the utilization of plasmon absorption band shift as an indicator (Fig. 3D). Maximum band shift and enzyme activity is observed for pH in 4–7 range where efficient O-Gly bond cleavage takes place. Increase of pH up to 9 results in significant suppression of enzyme activity and further increase of pH up to 10 or 11 leads to complete suppression of enzyme activity which is evident from conservation of plasmon absorption band position. Control experiments, performed without fiber surface functionalization does not show any shift of plasmon related absorption band for pH in 4–12 range (at lower or higher pH the acidic or alkaline induced cleavage of O-Gly bond can occurs, thus we exclude these pH values from our experiments, see Fig. S13). We compared our results obtained with those obtained using commercial kit (Fig. S14). Like in the previous case we observed perfect correlations – enzymatic activity was maximum in pH = 4 – 7 range and gradually decreases for higher pH. It should be stressed that we are able to determine enzyme activity and its suppression using the simple analytical procedure with utilization of proposed fiber optical probe, i.e. in more simple and express way, compared to utilisation of the standard kit.

In the next step, we also estimate the stability of the fibers after long-term storage at a decreased temperature (5 °C). For this goal, the Au-Gly fiber response on the presence and action of the enzyme was tested every week for one month. The results obtained (Fig. S15) indicate that there

are no changes in the sample response – similar shifts of the plasmon absorption band were observed for an aged and freshly prepared optical fiber probe. We also estimated the potential biofouling of the optical fiber surface during their interaction with simulated bio-liquid (BSA solution was used). As can be expected in the case of pristine (non-grafted) optical fiber, the apparent shift of the plasmon absorption band was observed, because of non-specific protein sorption on the naked Au surface. However, preliminary grafting of the fiber surface with Gly chemical moieties results in efficient screening of the Au surface, which prevents non-specific protein sorption and protects the fiber sensor against biofouling (Fig. S16).

In the last step, we confirmed the proposed mechanism of optical fiber probe action, i.e. the ability of enzyme to perform the full or partial cleavage of glycoside moieties. First, the thickness of grafted Au layer before and after the interaction with enzyme was estimated using AFM scratch tests (see Fig. 4A). As is evident, the pristine thickness of Au layer (ca 20 nm) is increased up to 40 nm after the immobilization of enzyme-responsive Gly layer. However, after the interaction with enzyme (RT, 20 min, pH=6) the thickness decreased to 25 nm, which indicates adlayers deposition of Au and residual $-C_6H_4-OH$ fragments (Fig. 4B, C). However, when the fiber probes were immersed in the solution at 80 °C or pH= 11, the apparent conservation of Au layer thickness was observed (Figs. S17 and S18). Apparently, the grafted organic layer was not removed in this case. Similar results were also obtained with FTIR spectroscopy of Au-Gly surface before and after interaction with β -Glucosidase. After the interaction a part of FTIR peaks disappears completely, while several bands, attributed to $-C_6H_4-OH$ (see Fig. 4C) are conserved. So, FTIR spectroscopy and AFM scratch tests results confirm the proposed mechanism of enzymes activity detection.

It should also be noted that this work is mainly aimed at demonstration of an alternative principle of using optical fibers for local detection of enzymatic activity. It should be noted that optical fibers have been used previously for similar purposes (Table S2) [31–38]. In most of the reported cases, the function of the optical fiber was to collect the optical signal obtained by fluorescence or chemiluminescence excitation (or changes in the absorption spectrum of added dye(s)).

Fig. 4. Conformation of enzyme triggered cleavage of grafted organic moieties: A - AFM-based scratch tests performed before Gly grafting and after interaction fiber probe with enzyme solution; B - schematic representation of glycoside bond cleavage in enzyme solution; C - FTIR spectra measured on a previously grafted Au surface, indicating the removal of glycoside moieties.

Without a doubt, such an approach allows one to achieve detection parameters (response range, time of response) that are no worse than in our case (Table S2). However, such approaches also involve the addition of dyes or biologically active molecules to the sample. Thus, detection should be performed in a separately selected sample, without the possibility of directly measuring the enzymatic activity in the entire system without violating its integrity (for example, performing measurements directly in a biological reactor). In our case, however, the sensor design provides for such a possibility, since there is no need to collect a sample and the enzymatic activity can be directly measured by the introduction of optical fibre into the enzymatic system, with minimal impact on this system itself.

In this work, we used the fiber probe with previously optimised lengths of plasmon active area (Fig. S1). In particular, the length of the plasmon active area was 2 cm, which ensures efficient excitation of plasmonic wave and probing of the external environment. Such a design can allow for the in-situ detection in such systems as chemical or biochemical reactors. However, plasmon active area can be deposited on the polished fiber end, which opens the possibility of a local detection of enzymatic activity, with a spatial resolution of the order of several microns.

Generally, we rather demonstrated the principal concept of detection, based on a relatively simple “enzyme-substrate” system, but, in the future, this concept can be expanded to a range of alternative reactions, e.g. by grafting various substrates onto plasmon-active optical fibers and their enzymatic cleavage, monitored as a shift of the plasmon absorption band in back-reflected light. In this light, sensor utilisation can include areas of application such as in-situ monitoring of enzyme activity in the biochemical reactors or in living tissue. In addition, the proposed sensor can be directly used for the estimation of the bacteria-associated activity in the outside conditions, such as the monitoring of the soil or water environment.

4. Conclusion

In this work, the simple, optical fiber-based sensor for express and unpretentious estimation of enzyme activity was proposed. The suggested approach is based on the functionalization of the surface of plasmon active optical fiber with glycoside moieties. The excitation of plasmon produce an optical absorption band (measured in the back-reflected light), spectral position of which is depends on the local environment, affected by enzyme action. In the enzyme presence, the -C-O-bond in glycoside is cleaved, which leads to a change in the local surface chemistry and corresponding shift in plasmon absorption band spectral position. The proposed approach was tested under “optimal” conditions, and the optical fiber response on the enzyme presence and concentration was evident. In addition, the suppression of enzyme activity by external temperature or pH were also tested. In this case, the absence or less pronounced plasmon absorption band shift (i.e. absence of enzymatic bond cleavage) was observed at higher temperatures or „unfavorable“ pH values. Generally, the proposed approach allows very simple and express detection of enzymatic activity. Moreover, the procedure can be performed in situ, with a minimal distortion introduced to enzyme-related catalytic or biochemical system. We demonstrated the advantages of the present approach on the simple biochemical system (β -Glucosidase enzyme and glycoside substrate), but a similar concept can be expanded to the range of alternative enzymes and corresponded substrates.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yuliia Viktosenko: Investigation. **Denis Vasilev:** Investigation. **Elena Stepanova:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Alina Gorbunova:** Methodology, Investigation. **David Mares:** Investigation. **Anastasiia Skvortsova:** Methodology, Investigation. **Vasilii Burtsev:** Investigation. **Pavel Postnikov:** Writing

– review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Elena Miliutina:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Oleksiy Lyutakov:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision. **Zdenka Kolska:** Validation, Methodology. **Václav Švorčík:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supporting Information

Preparation and characterization of grafting agent. Schematic representation of plasmon-Induced Unsymmetric IS Cleavage and experimental set-up used for estimation of enzyme activity. High-resolution XPS spectra, SEM-measured surface morphology. AFM scratch tests. Control experiments results (absence of enzyme, previous enzyme denaturation), temperature dependence. Estimation of β -glucosidase activity as a function of temperature and pH. Affiliation of FTIR bands.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.snb.2025.138872](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2025.138872).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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